

STUDY OF RISK FACTORS OF CHORIOAMNIONITIS DEVELOPMENT IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH PREGNANCY WATER LOSS

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the study of risk factors of chorioamnionitis development in pregnant women with pregnancy water loss. Chorioamnionitis is a common complication of pregnancy associated with significant maternal, perinatal, and long-term adverse outcomes. Adverse maternal outcomes include postpartum infections and sepsis while adverse infant outcomes include stillbirth, premature birth, neonatal sepsis, chronic lung disease and brain injury leading to cerebral palsy and other neurodevelopmental disabilities. Research in the last two decades has expanded our understanding of the mechanistic links between intraamniotic infection and preterm delivery as well as morbidities of preterm and term infants. Recent and ongoing clinical research into better methods for diagnosing, treating and preventing chorioamnionitis is likely to have a substantial impact on short and long-term outcomes in the neonate.

Definition

Pregnancy begins in a woman with the maturation of an egg and its successful implantation in the uterus after fertilization by a male sperm cell.

And on average, it lasts 40 weeks, or 280 days. This period is conditionally divided into three trimesters, or trimesters. Tracking periods by weeks and trimesters is also convenient for pregnant women.

One of the most important activities for a mother is to monitor changes in her pregnancy during the pregnancy. The calendar is very useful for the expectant mother to understand her body and the developing heart. Our team has developed a mobile app to track your pregnancy calendar. With this app, women can easily monitor changes in themselves and their fetuses.

Symptoms of pregnancy

The woman's body begins to prepare for pregnancy before the next ovulation, and after fertilization and implantation in the uterus, the woman begins to show early signs of pregnancy. These symptoms are caused by a number of hormonal changes in the body.

Against the background of hormonal changes, you may experience the first symptoms of menstrual irregularities, small amounts of bloody discharge, enlarged and

painful breasts, drowsiness, weakness, and nausea.

There are also secondary symptoms, the occurrence of which is considered as symptoms confirming the occurrence of pregnancy.

Determining fetal duration

Pregnancy begins on the last day of a woman's menstrual cycle. From this date, the average duration is 280 days and labor begins. Ultrasound examination can also be used to determine the duration.

Pregnancy trimesters

As mentioned above, the pregnancy calendar is conditionally divided into three to three months. These periods, in turn, include certain weeks. That is, the first trimester from week 1 to week 13, the second trimester from week 14 to week 26, and the third trimester from week 27 to week 40.

The first trimester is also known as the period of conception or adjustment for the fetus. This is the most delicate period of pregnancy and requires the mother to take

responsibility for her health and changes in her body. By the end of the trimester, the fetus is 7-8 cm long and weighs 25 g.

By the second trimester, you will be able to feel relief and happiness. During this period, the symptoms of toxicosis almost disappear, and other discomforts are reduced. Sometimes some pregnant women complain of sharp pains in the pelvis, abdomen and pelvis.

The third trimester can be considered as the stage of preparation for

childbirth. At the same time, your unborn child is growing and developing.

During the "waiting" period for the birth of your baby - movements that are important for life, sucking, swallowing, breathing, turning the head, moving the legs and arms.

Nutrition during pregnancy

If the fetus is developing without any discomfort, the pregnant woman should eat 4 times a day. Half of the protein in the daily diet should be animal protein (meat, fish - 25%, 20% - dairy products, 5% - eggs).

The need for vegetable protein is met by legumes (mung beans, peas, beans), rice, cabbage, and potatoes. In addition to sugar, it is advisable to use bread, cereals, fruits as a source of carbohydrates.

Beef, pork and mutton are not recommended during pregnancy. Learn more about products that are harmful to pregnant women and fetuses in this article: One of the main conditions for a successful pregnancy and good fetal development is good nutrition; The diet should be nutritious, varied, rich in protein and vitamins, including folic acid, vitamin C. For example, taking 400 mcg of folic acid a day before pregnancy reduces the risk of developing birth defects.

Pregnancy risk factors

Usually, acute problems do not occur when the pregnancy is normal. Problems can sometimes occur, so it's a good idea for every woman to be aware of the dangers of pregnancy.

During the follow-up of the pregnant woman, the doctor regularly conducts the necessary tests, examinations and tests to identify and eliminate any concerns. It is also important for a pregnant woman to be aware of her condition and to report any

dangerous symptoms to her doctor in a timely manner.

Pregnancy in pregnant women (high probability of miscarriage in the first 20 weeks of pregnancy), ectopic pregnancy, premature birth (if the child is born before 37 weeks, it is considered premature), preeclampsia, decreased amniotic fluid, gestational diabetes, placental abruption Factors such as exposure to the virus can be life-threatening for the mother and fetus.

Pregnancy and exercise

A pregnant woman should do light physical exercises. Depending on the stage of pregnancy, a special set of gymnastic exercises is recommended.

You can exercise for 30 minutes 5-7 times a week. It is recommended to start with 10 minutes a day and increase to 30 minutes. Regular exercise during pregnancy is an important factor in fetal development and ease of delivery.

Sex during pregnancy

Sex during pregnancy is safe in the absence of contraindications and restrictions. However, sexual intercourse should be avoided if a woman is at risk of miscarriage or other adverse conditions.

Having sex does not harm your unborn child. However, as a precaution, couples should agree on safe poses.

Changes in sexual orientation during pregnancy are normal for a woman. You don't have to worry about this, but it's helpful to talk to your partner about it. Some couples enjoy having sex during pregnancy, while others feel they don't want to. The most important thing is to talk to each other about your feelings and compromise. The pathogenesis of chorioamnionitis is marked by the passage of infectious organisms to the chorioamnion and / or umbilical cord of

the placenta Figures 1. This passage occurs most commonly by retrograde or ascending infection from the lower genital tract (cervix and vagina) (Figure 1). Hematogenous / transplacental passage and iatrogenic infection complicating amniocentesis or chorionic villous sampling are less common routes of infection. Anterograde infection from the peritoneum via the fallopian tubes has also been postulated. The presence of infectious agents in the chorioamnion engenders a maternal and fetal inflammatory response characterized by the release of a

combination of proinflammatory and inhibitory cytokines and chemokines in the maternal and fetal compartments (Figure1). The inflammatory response may produce clinical chorioamnionitis and / or lead to prostaglandin release, ripening of the cervix, membrane injury and labor at term or premature birth at earlier gestational ages. Aside from the risk of direct fetal infection and sepsis, the fetal inflammatory response may induce cerebral white matter injury, which may result in cerebral palsy and other short and long-term neurological deficits (Figure 1).

Figure-1. Mechanisms of chorioamnionitis and its associated complications

Clinical Signs and Symptoms

The key clinical findings associated with clinical chorioamnionitis include fever, uterine fundal tenderness, maternal tachycardia (>100/min), fetal tachycardia (>160/min) and purulent or foul amniotic fluid. Maternal fever is the most important

clinical sign of chorioamnionitis. Temperature > 100.4°F is considered abnormal in pregnancy. While isolated low-grade fever (<101°F) may be transient in labor, fever >100.4°F persisting more than 1h or any fever ≥101°F warrants evaluation and appropriate intervention. Fever is present in 95–100% of cases of clinical chorioamnionitis and typically is required for the diagnosis (see below). Fever in the

setting of epidural anesthesia, particularly among nulliparous women with prolonged labor (so called epidural fever) is often encountered and poses a diagnostic quagmire vis-à-vis chorioamnionitis. This is because i) in addition to fever, the two conditions share other major risk factors (low parity and prolonged labor), ii) epidural anesthesia masks signs of chorioamnionitis such as fundal tenderness, and iii) medications given during epidural anesthesia may induce maternal or fetal tachycardia and therefore confound the diagnosis of chorioamnionitis. The exact mechanism of epidural fever is unknown, but it is thought to be the result of epidural sympathetic blockade of thermoregulatory processes such as sweating. In one study, maternal fever was more common among the epidural group when placental inflammation was present (35% vs. 17%) but not in the absence of inflammation (11% vs. 9%). This suggests that the pathologic basis for epidural fever is chorioamnionitis. In sum, the concept of epidural fever remains controversial and warrants additional studies.

Maternal tachycardia (>100 BPM) and fetal tachycardia (>160 BPM) occur frequently in chorioamnionitis, being reported in 50–80% and 40–70% of cases respectively. Tachycardia may be present in the absence of chorioamnionitis and requires careful assessment for alternative etiologies. Medications such as ephedrine, antihistamines, and beta agonists may raise

maternal or fetal heart rate. However, the combination of maternal fever and maternal and/or fetal tachycardia are strongly suggestive of intrauterine infection and should be treated accordingly.

Aside from the objective measurements of maternal fever and tachycardia, other signs of chorioamnionitis are highly subjective. Uterine fundal tenderness and a foul odor to the amniotic fluid are reported in only 4–25% of cases of chorioamnionitis. Fundal tenderness is difficult to interpret in the context of the pain of labor and may be masked by analgesics including epidural or confounded by the pain associated with placental abruption. Purulence or foul odor of amniotic fluid are more likely to be present with severe or prolonged infection and may be organism-specific, but in any case may or may not be appreciated by clinicians.

Chorioamnionitis that is subclinical by definition does not present the above clinical signs but may manifest as preterm labor or, even more commonly, as preterm premature rupture of membranes (PPROM). In addition, premature ROM at term (membrane rupture at ≥ 37 weeks gestation but prior to onset of uterine contractions), which occurs in 8% or less of term births, is associated with an increased risk of chorioamnionitis

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